

Composition of *Parkia* Oil.

BY DINKER RAMCHANDRA PARANJPE.

Oil from the seeds of *Parkia Biglandulosa*, akin to *Parkia Africana*, which is exotic but found to thrive well in Bangalore, has been examined in the present paper.

It was extracted with petroleum ether (60° to 80°) from the crushed seeds and a pale yellow oil having a peculiar odour was obtained with an yield of 16.5 g.

On examination it was found that the oil contained a fairly large amount of combined behenic acid besides the glycerides of oleic, linoleic, palmitic and stearic acids. These have been estimated quantitatively. The results show that the abnormal proportion of behenic acid as also that of unsaturated acids are somewhat unusual when the constituents of other oils are compared.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The analytical constants of the oil given in Table I were determined on the usual lines and are compared with the values given by Lewkowitsch (Chemical technology of oils, fats and waxes) for *Parkia Africana* which appear in the second column.

TABLE I.

	<i>Parkia</i> - <i>Biglandulosa</i> . (Paranjpe).	<i>Parkia</i> - <i>Africana</i> . (Lewkowitsch).
Specific gravity (15°)	... 0.9208	—
$n_D^{21.2}$... 1.4705	—
Saponification value	... 189.5	184.0
Iodine value	... 80.87	91.6
Polensky value	... 0.25	—
Reichert-Meisel value	... 1.12	0.6
Acid value	... 5.2	—
Acetyl value	... nil	—
Unsaponifiable matter	... 1.11%	—
Hehner value	... 94.7	95.5

The mixed fatty acids.—The mixed fatty acids were prepared by saponifying the oil with alcoholic solution of sodium hydroxide, the dried soap extracted with ether to remove the unsaponifiable matter, and the fatty acids regenerated from the soap by boiling with dilute hydrochloric acid. Analyses gave the following results—

TABLE II.

Mean mol. weight	290·2
Iodine value	101·6
Titre	39°·5

The mixed acids were separated into the saturated and unsaturated acids by the method of Twitchell (*J. Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1921, 13, 806). The process was repeated twice and the separated acids were analysed with results given below.

TABLE III.

		Saturated (30 per cent.) Acids.	Unsaturated (70 per cent.) Acids.
Eq. weight	...	288·0	288·0
Iodine value	...	1·2	141·5
Refractive index	...	n_D^{65} 1·4371	n_D^{45} 1·4582
Titre	...	54°·0	...

Examination of the unsaturated acids.—The additive bromo-compounds were prepared by the method of Jamieson and Baughman (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1920, 42, 2398). Unsaturated acids (5 g.) were dissolved in dry ether (100 c.c.) and treated with glacial acetic acid (2 c. c.). The mixture was cooled in ice and brominated with dry bromine ; on leaving in ice for six hours, no precipitate of hexabromide separated out showing the absence of linolenic acid. In the absence of linolenic acid the mixture of the bromides was washed with water to free it from acetic acid, and then with hypo solution to remove excess of bromine. The ethereal layer was then dried with calcium chloride and finally evaporated on the water-bath. The increase in weight on bromination of the fatty acids is in fair agreement with

the proportion of oleic to linolic, worked out from the iodine value of the unsaturated acids. The bromination results are given below.

TABLE IV.

Quantity brominated	...	7.6130	5.7004 g.
Hexabromides	...	<i>nil.</i>	<i>nil.</i>
Yield of di- and tetrabromides	...	14.2845	10.7090 g.
Calculated yield according to oleic : linolic as 43.7 : 56.3 from iodine value	...	14.3950	10.7764 g.
M.p. of tetrabromide (cryst. from petrol)	...	113°.	113°.

The proportion of oleic to linolic thus arrived at was oleic : linolic as 43.7 : 56.3.

Examination of the saturated acids.—Saturated acids (175 g.) were collected from various separations and recoveries from the insoluble lead salts.

It was found from a qualitative test that a portion of these acids was sparingly soluble in cold ether. The acid obtained from this separation was further crystallised and was identified as behenic acid, from the molecular weight and the melting point tests. The melting point of this acid was 80-81°.

This separation was undertaken with the whole lot. A 10 p.c. ether solution of the acids was cooled to 0° and after four hours the precipitated acids were filtered and washed with cold ether. The proportion of the ether insoluble acids on the total acids was 12.8 p. c.

The ether insoluble acids had an equivalent weight of 324.3 and m.p. 73°; this corresponded to a point on the stearic-behenic acids melting point curve, where the proportion of behenic acid is 72 p. c. (Sudborough, Watson and Ayyar, *J. Indian Inst. Sci.*, 1926, **9A**, Part II, Fig. 3).

The ether soluble saturated acids were recovered and converted into methyl esters by boiling with ten times their volume of anhydrous methyl alcohol containing 4 p. c. hydrogen chloride. The purified esters were subjected to a preliminary fractional distillation under reduced pressure, and then subjected to a second fractionation at 5 mm. pressure.

The results of the refractionation are given in Table V.

TABLE V.

Fraction No.	Boiling range (5 mm.).	Yield.	Titre of ester.	M. W. of ester.	M. p. of acids.
I	175°	9.64g.	23.5°	272.0	58.0°
II	175-181	15.35	25.0°	277.7	55.5°
III	181-186	16.11	26.5°	280.6	56.0°
IV	186-188	13.94	28.9°	287.0	58.5°
V	188-195	16.97	30.3°	289.9	60.5°
VI	195-201	7.10	33.7°	302.1	60.5°
VII	201-210	11.90	37.4°	311.8	63.0°
VIII	210-220	14.27	42.4°	327.6	65.0°
IX	220-229	9.78	47.0°	340.4	73.4°
Residue	—	5.20	—	—	—

Fraction I was liquid, it was cooled to 20° to partially crystallise and then quickly filtered through a small Buchner funnel. The equivalent of the esters in the filtrate was 271, similarly the titre was not appreciably changed. The ester was then decomposed into acid and the acid crystallised from 70 p. c. alcohol. In the partial crystallisation from alcohol, the crystallised acids were filtered out and the filtrate was evaporated to obtain the lower acid. It was found to be almost pure palmitic acid from the equivalent weight determination and a mixed m.p. test with a pure specimen.

According to mixture tables (*J. Indian Inst. Sci.*, 1923; 6, 126; Lewkowitsch, *loc. cit.*) the first five fractions seem to be mixtures of palmitic and stearic acids from the consideration of the titres and equivalent weights of the esters, and they are calculated as such.

Fraction VI has an equivalent weight of 302.1 and a titre 33.7°; if this is assumed to be a mixture of stearic with the other higher acid, which was found to be behenic acid, then according to mixture tables (*loc. cit.*) the titre should be 34° and the m.p. of the acids 66.5°, but the observed m.p. of the acids liberated from the fraction was much lower. A detailed examination of the remaining fractions showed that they were simple binary mixtures of stearic and behenic acids. The lower m.p. of fraction VI is in all probability due to traces of palmitic acid. Since no other acids excepting

palmitic, stearic and behenic are present in all the fractions, a small quantity of palmitic acid if present in fraction VI would not affect the final calculations materially ; therefore fraction VI was not subjected to any further examination.

The residue was crystallised four times from methyl alcohol and pale brown coloured flakes were obtained. The titre of the purified ester was 51.5° . The liberated acids from the above had an equivalent weight of 339.5 which did not rise on repeated crystallisations from 98 p. c. alcohol. It was therefore inferred that it was all behenic acid.

Fraction IX was carefully examined to see if any other higher acid was present. It was crystallised from methyl alcohol three times and then finally decomposed into acids. The acids were repeatedly crystallised from 98 p. c. alcohol and afterwards from cold ether. The equivalent weight did not rise above 340 and similarly the m.p. was fairly steady at 80° - 81° . The mixed melting point with a pure sample of behenic acid (m.p. 80 - 81°) did not show any change and it was therefore nothing else but behenic acid.

Details regarding the saturated esters are summarised in Table VI.

TABLE VI.

Fraction.	Palmitic ester.	Stearic ester.	Behenic ester.
I	8.95g.	0.69 g.	...
II	11.13	4.22	...
III	9.99	6.12	...
IV	5.48	8.46	...
V	4.91	12.06	...
VI	...	6.59	0.51g.
VII	...	8.96	2.94
VIII	...	6.72	7.55
IX	...	2.39	7.39
Residue	5.20
120.26 g.	40.46	56.21	23.59
The ether insoluble portion (calculated as ester)			
17.65 g.*	...	4.95 g.	12.71
Total of saturated esters			
137.91 g.	40.46	61.15	36.30

*The percentage of the ether insoluble acids, separated previously was 12.8 per cent. in the original saturated acids ; hence the equivalent of the ether insoluble acids for 120.26 g. of the ether soluble esters works out to 17.65 g.

The unsaponifiable matter.—The unsaponifiable matter, obtained from the extraction of the dry soap with petrol ether was in a nicely crystallised condition. About one gram of the same was treated with one p. c. boiling digitonin solution. On cooling overnight a precipitate was obtained, which was filtered and weighed after drying. This gave 21.22 p. c. of sterols in the unsaponifiable matter. The acetyl derivative was prepared from the digitonin compound and crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 125.5°. This shows that sitosterol is present in the unsaponifiable matter.

The composition of the Pakira oil fatty acids works out as follows:—

Oleic acid 30.6 p.c.; linoleic acid 39.4 p.c.; palmitic acid 8.8 p.c.; stearic acid 13.3 p.c.; behenic acid 39.4 p.c.

Summary.

The oil obtained from the seeds of *Parkia Biglandulosa* (grown in Bangalore, S. India) has been examined in detail and its composition determined. It has been found that while the oil contains as much as 7.9 per cent of the behenic acid, it also contains 39.4 per cent. the unsaturated linoleic acid. The oil can therefore be used as a source of behenic acid which is somewhat rare.

In conclusion I wish to tender my heartfelt thanks to Prof. H. E. Watson and Mr. P. R. Ayyar of the Indian Institute of Science, Bangalore, for their kind interest in this investigation.

DEPARTMENT OF CHEMISTRY
COLLEGE OF SCIENCE, NAGPUR.

Received March 17, 1931.